

FINITE ELEMENT MODELING OF BALLISTIC IMPACT ON MULTI-LAYER WOVEN FABRICS

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1. Introduction

Woven fabrics composed of light weight and high strength continuous filaments are especially useful in a wide-range of applications such as protective materials for military and law enforcement personnel and as well as structural containment of turbine fragments [1]. The engine containment system is typically constructed by wrapping multiple layers of Kevlar 49 around a thin aluminum encasement. Designing the containment system consists of determining the type of fabric, the number of fabric layers and fabric width required. Currently the FAA's certification standards require that a full-scale test be completed to qualify an engine which can cost several million dollars [2]. Consequently, there is a continuing effort to reduce the extent of these experimental test programs by complementing them with the corresponding computation-based engineering analyses and simulations. Modeling the impact response of woven fabrics is challenging because of their intricate hierarchical architectures, complex material behavior and interactions between the projectile and fabric during transverse impact. There are several modeling techniques used to represent the impact behavior of flexible woven fabrics. The impact behavior can be analyzed by using pin-jointed orthogonal bars in finite element analyses [3]. Unit-cell based approaches have been used extensively in order to derive the equivalent (smeared) continuum-level material models of woven composites from the knowledge of the meso-scale yarn properties, fabric architecture and inter-yarn and inter-ply frictional characteristics [4]. More-detailed 3D continuum finite element analyses [5] have proven to be powerful tools for capturing and elucidating the detailed dynamic response of single-layer fabric, they are associated with large computational

requirements in terms of both processing power and memory requirement because of the large number of degrees of freedom of the model. This limits the size of the fabric model that can be simulated within available computational infrastructure and reasonable amount of time.

In our previous study [6], a material model (ASU v.1.1) was developed to include non-linearity in the stress-strain response and strain rate effect on the material response as part of the project on explicit finite element modeling of multi-layer composite fabric for gas turbine engine containment systems [7-15]. The fabric layers were represented by one single finite element (FE) layer; hence it was not able to capture the effect of friction between the fabrics layers which is actually an important factor for determining the ballistic behavior of the fabric. Later on, a multi-layer model (ASU v.1.2) was built to consider the friction between the fabric layers [16]. But all these models were built on the experimental data where the fabric was loaded up to the strain of about 4% [8, 17], and the post-peak behaviors were assumed to follow certain patterns without experimental validation. New experimental data show that the fabric can deform up to 20% before the complete failure, the energy absorption ability will dramatically increase due to the large strain capacity [13, 18]. In this study, we extend our previous work by optimizing material/model parameters in a modified UMAT subroutine which is based on a constitutive behavior from the new data.

2. Constitutive Model of Woven Fabric

New tensile tests were conducted in both warp and fill directions until the load carrying capacity of the fabric reached zero, the results show that the fabric can deform up to 20% before the complete failure.

Figure 1 shows the new stress-strain curves of quasi-static tensile test using 200 mm × 50 mm (length × width) swath specimens and the material model developed for the fabric in the warp and fill directions. Note that there are four distinct regions in the constitutive behavior: crimp region, linear pre-peak region, linear post-peak region and non-linear post-peak region. In the crimp region, the stress increase is relative low due to the straightening of the woven structure of the fabric. When the crimp is removed, the straightened yarns start to behave linearly and take more loads, reaching linear pre-peak region. When the stress level reaches the tensile strength of the fabric the yarns start to break and the stress of the fabric decreases dramatically until reaching a transition point which is about 70 MPa (linear post-peak region). After the transition point the stress decreases gradually to almost zero when the strain reaches to about 0.2 mm/mm, representing the non-linear post-peak region.

Fig. 1. Stress-strain curves of Kevlar 49 fabric in the (a) warp and (b) fill directions (experiment and model)

Based on the stress-strain curves in the warp and the fill directions, it was found that the elastic stiffness in pre-peak region of warp direction is identical to that of fill direction, and the crimp stiffness for warp and fill directions is 0.06 and 0.20 times of the elastic stiffness in pre-peak region, respectively. The stiffness in linear post-peak region of warp and fill directions is 2.2 and 5.6 times of the elastic stiffness in pre-peak region. The crimp strain of the warp direction is about 2.6 times larger than that of the fill direction. And the peak stress of the warp direction is 15% lower than that of the fill direction. There is a slight difference in the strain at peak stress and the stiffness of linear post-peak region.

The strain-rate effect is considered using a Cowper-Symonds (CS) model. In the current material model, the elastic stiffness and strain at peak stress were assumed to be a function of the strain rate using CS model. In such a way, the peak stress was indirectly assumed to be a function of the strain rate. But the fabric under ballistic impact might experience much higher strain rate than the available experimental data and the extrapolation process will introduce some uncertainties in the simulation results, it is necessary to optimize these two values to achieve better simulation results. Picture frame test has been conducted to determine the shear behavior of Kevlar 49 fabric [18]. In the experiment study, the fabric was sheared at quasi-static loading rate without any pretension and it has very low shear resistance. But in real ballistic scenario, the fabric under impact will experience large tensile force during shear deformation. The tension force in the fabric will dramatically influence the shear resistance of the fabric by altering the conditions of the yarn interaction (crimp, yarn compression, normal force at cross-over points), and hence the friction. If the shear properties of the fabric obtained by picture frame test were used directly in FE simulation, the fabric behaves like a rubber-like material with very large deformation. As the relation between shear properties and tensile stress in fabric is not clear, the shear properties used in the FE simulation was adjusted until the deformation of the fabric in simulation was similar to that of the experiment, and then was optimized to obtain the smallest error in absorbed energy between the simulations and experiments.

3. NASA Ballistic Tests

To help validate the material model, NASA-GRC conducted ballistic tests in which projectiles were fired at fabric wrapped around a steel ring. The loss of projectile kinetic energy (absorbed energy) ΔE_{pk} is the difference in the kinetic energy of the projectile. To help validate the material model, NASA-GRC conducted ballistic tests in which projectiles were fired at fabric wrapped around a steel ring [19]. Various parameters were varied during the tests. These parameters included the initial velocity of the projectile, the orientation of the projectile with respect to the fabric, the number of layers wrapped around the ring, the type of projectile, etc. For each test the initial and final velocity of the projectile was measured so were the exact orientation of the projectile [16]. The loss of projectile kinetic energy (absorbed energy), ΔE_{pk} is computed as the kinetic energy of the projectile before impact minus the kinetic energy of the projectile after impact, as follows:

$$\Delta E_{pk} = E_i - E_r = \frac{1}{2} m (v_i^2 - v_r^2) \quad (1)$$

where m is the mass of the projectile, v_i the projectile initial velocity, and v_r the projectile residual velocity.

The difference in absorbed energy between experiments and simulations was computed as:

$$D = \Delta E_{pk}^{\text{exp}} - \Delta E_{pk}^{\text{sim}} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta E_{pk}^{\text{exp}}$ is the absorbed energy in experiment, and $\Delta E_{pk}^{\text{sim}}$ the absorbed energy in simulation.

4. Finite Element Modeling

The model configuration is sub-divided into single-layer (SL) and multi-layer (ML) models. In the SL model (Fig. 2a), one finite element layer is used to represent all the physical layers in the model. Each fabric layer is 0.28 mm thick. Thus an 8-layer physical model is represented by one FE layer with a

thickness of 2.24 mm (8×0.28 mm). The fabric model was meshed using two different parts. The fabric directly in contact with penetrator is given separate part id than rest of the fabric. This type of configuration facilitates tracing of energy balance for this area separately. The SL model is computationally efficient which makes it beneficial for initial studies. However fabric-to-fabric contact cannot be modeled as well as the extent of the damage cannot be gauged. In the ML model (Fig. 2b), one FE layer represents four physical layers. Hence an 8 layer model is represented by 2 FE layers each having a thickness of 1.12 mm (4×0.28 mm).

The simulations were run using the single precision LS-DYNA version 971 R4.2.1. The FORTRAN compiler used for building the executable was Intel Version 10.1 and the computer platform was Windows XP 32bit single precision. As mentioned in the section of constitutive model, some of the material properties should be obtained by optimizing their values so as to reduce the error in the energy absorbed.

Fig. 2. Finite element models of (a) SL and (b) ML

5. Optimization of Material Properties

Five material parameters ($G_{12}^I, \gamma_{12}^I, \gamma_{12}^{II}, C = C_E = C_\epsilon$ and $P = P_E = P_\epsilon$) have been chosen as the design factors which have two levels (lower and upper) to minimize the response which is the difference between the experiments and simulations using a software named *Design Expert*, as listed in Table 1. A 2^5 full factorial design was used in the optimization design which required 32 runs for each test using SL FE model. Note that 22 tests were used for this study.

Table 1. Design factors and their levels

Level	G_{12}^I (MPa)	γ_{12}^I	γ_{12}^{II}	C_E	P_E
Lower	2.76	0.25	0.35	0.005	10
Upper	6.90	0.34	0.65	0.025	50

Figure 3(a) shows the half-normal Plot which indicates the effects of various factors and interactions from the model. Based on this graph, where the response variable is the percent difference in absorbed energy, the factors (G_{12}^I, γ_{12}^I and γ_{12}^{II}) that lie along the line are not significant and two factors (C and P) and the interactions with the factor P seem to be significant. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) shows that the full factorial model is significant as the model F-value is 468.71. There is only a 0.01% chance that a "Model F-Value" this large could occur due to noise. The adequacy of the underlying model should be checked before the conclusions from the analysis of variance are adopted. Violation of the basic assumptions and model adequacy can be easily investigated by the examination of residuals. For example, if the model is adequate, the residuals should be structure less and that is, they should contain no obvious patterns. Figure 3(b) presents a normal probability plot of the residuals for tensile strength. All the data points lie along a pretty straight line. It tells us that there is no violation of normality assumption, nor is there any evidence pointing to possible outliers. The final equation in terms of coded factors of the model is given as:

$$F = -14.98 - 0.0022G_{12}^I + 0.34\gamma_{12}^I - 1.07\gamma_{12}^{II} + 3.08C + 29.21P - 3.56\gamma_{12}^{II}P + 2.32CP \quad (3)$$

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. (a) Half-normal plot of the response for full model; and (b) normal probability plot of residuals

Using the optimization function in the software, the optimal values of the five factors are obtained as the following: $G_{12}^I = 4.14$ MPa (600 psi), $\gamma_{12}^I = 0.25$, $\gamma_{12}^{II} = 0.35$, $C = C_E = C_\epsilon = 0.005$ and $P = P_E = P_\epsilon = 40$. The actual shear modulus values at various shear strain values used in the material model can be

determined as follows: $G_{12}^I = 4.14 \text{ MPa}$ ($\gamma_{12} < \gamma_{12}^I$), $G_{12}^{II} = 41.4 \text{ MPa}$ ($\gamma_{12}^I < \gamma_{12} < \gamma_{12}^{II}$), $G_{12}^{III} = 345 \text{ MPa}$ ($\gamma_{12} > \gamma_{12}^{II}$). A conservatively low value of 345 MPa was assumed as the out of plane shear modulus for G_{23} and G_{31} .

6. Simulation Results

Figure 4 and 5 show the comparison of deformation between the simulation and the experiment for test cases of LG594 (SL) and LG429 (ML), respectively. It appears that the simulation captures the general deformed shape of the fabric. The comparisons of velocities and absorbed energy between the LS-DYNA simulations using SL and ML models and the experiments are listed in Table 2.

Fig. 4. Comparison of simulation and experiment for LG594 (SL)

Fig. 5. Comparison of simulation and experiment for LG429 (ML)

The single-layer model under-predicts 18 out of the 22 models and the percent different in the absorbed energy increases with increasing number of fabric layers (increasing thickness of FE layer). The multi-layer model under-predicts 18 out of the 19 models, and the percent different in the absorbed energy also increases with increasing number of fabric layers. The possible reason is that the outer layers of FE model break prematurely, resulting in relative less resistance against the projectile when comparing with the models with less FE layers. The single-layer model performs better than the multi-layer model as the single-layer model predicts the ballistic tests with less error and standard deviation in terms of the percent difference in absorbed energy. On the average, both of the models under-predict the absorbed energy and are conservative.

Table 2. Absorbed energy by the fabric for SL and ML FE simulations

Name	Fabric Layers	SL FE Simulation					ML FE Simulation				
		V_i (m/s)	V_r (m/s)	ΔE_{pk} (J)	%	D %	V_i (m/s)	V_r (m/s)	ΔE_{pk} (J)	%	D %
LG403	4	274.1	264.1	845	7.1	4.2	-	-	-	-	-
LG410	4	277.9	271.0	597	4.9	4.9	-	-	-	-	-
LG404	8	273.0	251.5	1782	15.1	1.0	273.0	254.2	1570	13.3	2.8
LG409	8	271.0	249.4	1778	15.3	2.3	271.0	251.8	1584	13.7	3.9
LG424	8	254.0	228.9	1917	18.8	1.3	254.0	229.7	1854	18.2	1.9
LG594	8	257.3	140.0	7254	69.9	-2.9	257.3	158.6	6381	61.5	5.5
LG609	8	278.7	260.6	1523	12.5	5.9	278.7	265.0	1163	9.6	8.8
LG610	8	270.8	247.4	1894	16.5	0.4	270.8	258.1	1052	9.2	7.7
LG611	8	276.1	258.7	1459	12.1	10.2	276.1	257.4	1575	13.1	9.3
LG612	8	273.8	258.8	1254	10.6	5.5	273.8	257.1	1394	11.8	4.3
LG618	8	264.2	160.1	6773	61.9	-3.5	-	-	-	-	-
LG620	8	272.6	190.7	5858	50.3	7.5	272.6	196.2	5496	47.2	10.6
LG689	8	273.3	201.7	5301	45.0	1.6	273.3	235.2	3029	25.7	20.9
LG692	8	269.7	194.9	5376	46.8	6.8	269.7	216.4	4006	34.9	18.8
LG429	16	278.9	234.5	3596	29.3	9.1	278.9	246.4	2694	22.0	16.4
LG432	16	273.0	216.0	4389	37.3	10.1	273.0	235.8	2992	25.4	22.0
LG405	24	274.1	188.6	6230	52.6	17.1	274.1	216.5	4449	37.5	32.1
LG411	24	270.0	149.1	7972	69.3	8.9	270.0	206.8	4743	41.2	37.0
LG427	24	278.9	174.6	7455	60.7	-4.7	278.9	215.1	4965	40.5	15.6
LG655	32	344.9	295.5	4981	26.5	19.6	344.9	317.7	2843	15.1	31.0
LG656	32	294.9	196.7	7602	55.4	21.1	294.9	208.4	6836	49.8	26.6
LG657	32	252.9	0.0	10090	100	0.0	252.9	0.0	10090	100	0.0
Average						5.7					14.5
Minimum						-4.7					0
Maximum						21.1					37.0
Std. Dev.						7.0					11.3

7. Conclusion

The continuum model developed in previous research has been improved by modifying the stress-strain constitutive behavior and the shear properties. The parameters (C and P) in Cowper-Symonds (CS) model and shear properties of the fabric were optimized to achieve better agreement between the simulations and the ballistic impact tests from NASA-GRC. The models were validated by comparing the residual velocity of the projectile and the absorbed energy by the fabric after the impact, and the spatial distribution of fabric deformation and damage. The single layer model was computationally efficient and predicted the ballistic tests with less error than the multi-layer model, while the latter was able to consider the friction between fabric layers.

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